

SIMULATING COMPRESSION-INDUCED RESIN TRANSFER FROM A SATURATED NON-WOVEN INTO A DRY FIBER STRUCTURE

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ABSTRACT

A new addition to the family of liquid composite molding (LCM) manufacturing processes termed resin transfer impregnation (RTI) has been proposed. The innovative process aims to improve cycle times and process efficiency, increase robustness and simplify overall process build-up, as no extensive injection and venting strategies are required. The process itself involves three constituents, resin, a carrier material and reinforcement. The carrier material is first saturated with resin and then stacked together with the dry reinforcement. The entire stack is then compressed, so that a through-thickness resin transfer from the carrier material into the structural reinforcement takes place. The purpose of this paper is to develop the framework for an initial simulation model of the RTI concept. The model should be capable of describing the hydrodynamic compaction behavior which takes place in both the carrier material and reinforcement during the process and allow the prediction of the final thickness and fiber volume fraction of each material. A review of the literature shows several relevant models based on fully and partially saturated through thickness flows through highly deformable porous media, but to the best of the authors' knowledge, no actual model of the RTI process in any shape or form currently exists. A complete derivation of the governing equation for the RTI process is first carried out and the initial conditions and boundary conditions are specified. The numerical solution is formulated into a one-dimensional model and solved separately using COMSOL and a Finite Element procedure using MATLAB. A first glimpse into some of the information which can be evaluated from the model is presented.

1 INTRODUCTION

Liquid Composite Molding (LCM) is a popular group of processes used for the manufacturing of fiber reinforced polymer composites (FRPC). Nevertheless, actual industrial usage lags behind potential application, which can be explained by deficiencies concerning cycle times and robustness. In this study, a novel LCM process concept is developed to address these issues. The manufacturing concept, referred to as Resin Transfer Impregnation (RTI), is a simple 3-step procedure (Fig. 1): First, a carrier material, which may be a nonwoven textile, is fully saturated with resin. Second, the saturated carrier material is stacked with a dry structural reinforcement, which may be a textile-based preform or similar. In a third step, the entire stack is compressed, so that a through-thickness resin transfer from the carrier material into the structural reinforcement takes place.

Figure 1: Basic approach of the novel Resin Transfer Impregnation LCM process.

Several variations of the RTI concept are possible. These may involve the method of compression (e.g. in a press between rigid tooling or vacuum bagging), the stacking sequence, and the area of the preform covered with the carrier material. It is also optional whether the carrier material is removed following the process, or if it remains within the part, providing additional functionality such as reduced textile print-through on the surface of the part, or serves as a protection layer (against scratches etc.) for the structural reinforcement. Compared to other existing LCM processes, RTI should provide benefits in terms of cycle time and robustness, as the resin flow path length is reduced to only the preform thickness and a simple flow pattern is generated. The simplicity, resulting from the fact that no extensive injection and venting strategy is required, also contributes to the robustness.

The aim of the present study is to build-up and validate an initial simulation model of the RTI concept. Independent from the many possible variations of the process concept, the physical phenomena determining the process remain the same. The complex fluid-structure interaction resulting in non-uniform hydrodynamic compaction effects and a compaction controlled resin infusion rate provide the most challenging aspects for the development of a corresponding simulation model.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW

Many works over the last 20 years have focused on modelling the interaction of a fluid with a deformable solid porous medium and the way in which this affects fluid flow and the deformation of the medium. In the works of Jönsson et al. [1, 2] the governing equations for both steady state (saturated) and dynamic flow behavior for fluid flow through general deformable porous media were developed and implemented numerically. The simulations allowed for the calculation of time dependent porosity and flow at varying locations in a porous medium subjected to hydraulic pressure and/or mechanical loading. In the work of Ouahbi et al. [3] the focus was directed towards the Resin Film Infusion (RFI) process and the development and validation of a 1D numerical model for the hydrodynamic compaction which takes place during this specific process. Simacek [4], Bhat [5] and Merotte [6] progressively developed a resin flow analysis model for Compression Resin Transfer Molding (CRTM), which considered the process in three separate stages, eventually here also implementing a through thickness hydrodynamic fiber preform deformation during the so-called second stage of the process [6]. More recently, Danzi et al. [7] considered the case of through-thickness surface resin bleeding which occurs during the consolidation of pre-impregnated laminates. Using the derived governing equation, a 1D numerical model was developed and the time-dependent interactions between fluid flow and textile deformation were simulated using COMSOL® Multiphysics and compared with experiments. In Klunker [8] et al. a similar approach to that of Danzi was taken to investigate hydrodynamic compaction effects which occur during through-thickness saturated textile reinforcement permeability measurements. Here the numerical model was able to predict the fiber volume content inhomogeneity (lower fiber volume content at the inlet and higher fiber volume content at the outlet) which occurs with increasing injection pressure used during the measurement procedure.

A more fundamental basis and relevant source of literature for the present study can be found in the works of Preziosi [9], Farina [10] and Billi [11]. In Preziosi [9], the derivation of the governing equations for the infiltration of a fluid into an initially dry porous media is considered with an indication towards application in various composite material manufacturing processes. Deduced on the basis of the theory of mixtures, but ignoring any chemical reactions or phase changes, the equations are developed and applied to a 1D numerical model assuming a “stiff sponge” (non-linear elastic and perfectly recoverable) type response, meaning that no compaction relaxation of the dry material phase takes place upon the application of pressure during the infusion. The role and significance of inertia and viscoelastic effects are also discussed and formulations considering a more complex “Kelvin-Voigt sponge” are also suggested in the work. As in most LCM composite manufacturing situations, the applied pressure gradient driving resin infusion is much larger than the driving force due to capillary pressure [12]. This means that the assumption of a “slug flow” (or perfectly even flow front and the neglect of any contribution from the capillary pressure) regardless of whether a press or vacuum processes is used becomes valid. This case is once again addressed specifically with respect to

composite materials in Billi [11], who derives the governing partial differential equation (PDE) for the unidirectional infiltration of a pure incompressible fluid being forced onto a dry textile composite preform stack assuming the simpler “stiff sponge” response. In this work, the infiltration front is at the entrance of the dry porous material, which is compressed instantaneously under the full applied pressure. In other words, the short initial load transient to arrive at the applied pressure is not considered in the model and the dry porous medium is assumed to behave in a non-linear elastic manner and recovers (once infused) along the same stress-strain curve path as loading. Therefore, when one considers a one-dimensional case, two free boundaries exist: one given by the infiltrating fluid front (resin flow-front) and the other given by the material relaxation front of the preform (where the top of the stack is compressing down), which relaxes, once wet-out by the fluid. The governing equations are derived in both the Eulerian and Lagrangian framework, the latter of which allows significant simplification of the numerical problem. In Farina [10], the mathematical modeling of the compression molding of a fully saturated pre-impregnated composite prepreg stack is considered, with the compaction applied through constant pressure (or velocity profile) assigned to a rigid plate adjacent to the pre-wetted fabric preform. Here the governing equations are also developed in both the Lagrangian and Eulerian framework. It is interesting to note that in the cases of Farina [10] and Billi [11], shown schematically in Fig. 2, the exact same governing equation describing the hydrodynamic compaction behavior of both cases is deduced. Therefore, the differences between the models and solutions arise only due to the different types of boundary conditions applied. A recent review of literature on the application of mixture theory for processes involving deformable porous media in different scientific fields (which includes the work of Farina) can be found in the recent review by Siddique [13].

Figure 2: Case A: Farina [10] (left) and Case B: Billi [11] (right) type problems describing saturated and unsaturated resin flow in deformable porous media.

3 MODELLING THE RTI PROCESS

In the RTI process, one of the materials, the carrier, is first fully saturated with resin. This material is then stacked on top of a dry structural reinforcement. Finally, the stack is compressed. In the development of the model, it is assumed that there is no seepage of resin from the carrier material into the dry reinforcement before the commencement of compression. It is also assumed that there are no gravitational, inertial or capillary effects and that the dry structural reinforcement exhibits a non-linear elastic behaviour with perfect recovery and no relaxation.

3.1 Geometry and coordinate systems

The 1D model assumes that the carrier material and dry reinforcement have precisely the same cross sectional area A and that the former sits perfectly on top of the latter. The compression occurs perfectly in one direction only. It will also be assumed that the cross-sectional area does not change (or

changes negligibly) with compaction. The thickness of the wet carrier is $h_1(t)$ and the thickness of the dry reinforcement is $h_2(t)$. The thickness of the complete stack at any time is given by:

$$h(t) = h_1(t) + h_2(t) \quad (1)$$

Figure 3: Geometry, compaction of the stack, resin flow, effective stresses and permeability functions for all materials and phases of the 1D RTI process.

The material/Lagrangian coordinates \mathbf{X} gives the position of a particle at time zero, measured from the top of the RTI stack. A given particle has only one material coordinate, which does not change over time. The spatial/Eulerian coordinate $\mathbf{x}(\mathbf{X}, t)$, measured from the top, gives the position of a particle (that was initially at \mathbf{X}) at the current time t . At time zero, $\mathbf{x}(\mathbf{X}, 0) = \mathbf{X}$.

The movement of a single particle p over time and its 1D coordinates are shown in Fig. 4. The displacement of the compaction plate is given by $\delta(t)$, i.e. $\mathbf{x}(0, t) \equiv \delta(t)$.

Figure 4: Definition of coordinate system

3.2 Volume fraction

The local volume fraction at position \mathbf{x} is $\phi_s(\mathbf{x}, t)$, the ratio of the volume of solid to the total volume of a material element at the current time t . This is an Eulerian description. If \mathbf{x} is treated as a dependent variable of the independent variables (\mathbf{X}, t) , then the volume fraction can be expressed as $\phi_s(\mathbf{x}(\mathbf{X}, t))$, which is the equivalent Lagrangian description.

It will be assumed that the volume fractions of the reinforcement and carrier materials are initially uniform, and given by:

$$\phi_s^0 \equiv \begin{cases} \phi_{s2}^0, & h_1^0 < x \leq h^0 \\ \phi_{s1}^0, & 0 \leq x \leq h_1^0 \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

In the Eulerian description $\phi_s^0(\mathbf{x}, t)$ denotes the initial volume fraction of the particle currently at (\mathbf{x}, t) . In the Lagrangian description $\phi_s^0(\mathbf{X})$ denotes: the initial volume fraction of the particle initially at \mathbf{X} .

3.3 1D Compaction Model: Eulerian description

The complete set of equations governing the 1D response for the incompressible fluid and solid phases is:

$$\text{Conservation of mass (solid):} \quad \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\phi_s v_s) = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \frac{\phi_s^0}{\phi_s} = \frac{dx}{dX} \quad (3)$$

$$\text{Conservation of mass (fluid):} \quad \frac{\partial \phi_f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\phi_f v_f) = 0 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{Darcy's Law:} \quad \phi_f (v_f - v_s) = -\frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Equilibrium:} \quad \frac{\partial \sigma_{eff}}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = 0 \quad \text{or} \quad \sigma = \sigma_{eff} + p = \text{const} \quad (6)$$

$$\text{Volume fraction and porosity:} \quad \phi_s(x, t) + \phi_f(x, t) = 1 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{Permeability dependence:} \quad K = K(\phi_s(x, t)) \quad (8)$$

$$\text{Constitutive relation (solid):} \quad \sigma_{eff} = \sigma_{eff}(\phi_s(x, t)) \quad (9)$$

together with the boundary conditions and initial conditions. In these equations, ϕ_f, ϕ_s are the fluid and solid fractions respectively (porosity and volume fractions), p is the fluid pressure, v_f, v_s are the velocities of the fluid and solid respectively, and ϕ_s^0 is the (constant) initial solid fraction. Eqn. 6 here is Terzaghi's law. Assuming that the permeability K and effective stress σ_{eff} are known functions of the solid fraction, and that one fraction is known when the other is known, trivially through the fifth equation, this becomes a set of 4 equations in the 4 unknowns (one volume fraction, two velocities and the fluid pressure).

The set of equations can be reduced further: first, to 3 equations in 3 unknowns by eliminating one of the velocities. To do this, first, adding together the first two Eqns (3) and (4), (the mass conservation equations for incompressible solid and fluid phases), and using Eqn. 7, i.e. $\partial \phi_s / \partial t = -\partial \phi_f / \partial t$, gives:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x}(\phi_s v_s + \phi_f v_f) = 0 \quad (10)$$

The term inside the brackets in Eqn. 10 is the composite velocity. One of the velocities is eliminated by substituting Darcy's law into this equation, and then integrating the result, leading to:

$$\phi_s v_s + \phi_f v_f = v_c(t) \quad v_s - \frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = v_c(t), \quad v_f + \frac{\phi_s}{\phi_f} \frac{K}{\mu} \frac{\partial p}{\partial x} = v_c(t), \quad (11)$$

Substituting either of the latter two into the equilibrium Eqn. (6) gives a new equation, which is supplemented by the appropriate mass conservation equation, giving a set of two equations in two unknowns, the volume fraction and the velocity:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \sigma_{eff}}{\partial x} + \frac{\mu}{K} (v_s - v_c(t)) &= 0 & \frac{\partial \sigma_{eff}}{\partial x} + \frac{\phi_f}{\phi_s} \frac{\mu}{K} (v_c(t) - v_f) &= 0 \\ \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\phi_s v_s) &= 0 & \frac{\partial \phi_f}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial}{\partial x} (\phi_f v_f) &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

Finally, eliminating the phase velocity from either of these sets of equations leads to one equation in the unknown solid volume fraction:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\phi_s \frac{K(\phi_s)}{\mu} \frac{\partial \sigma_{eff}(\phi_s)}{\partial \phi_s} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \right) - v_c(t) \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial t} \quad (13)$$

This is a parabolic partial differential equation. In order to obtain a solution, one must specify the initial and boundary conditions, and also supply an expression for the composite velocity in terms of the solid volume fraction.

3.4 1D Compaction Model: Lagrangian description

Eqn. 13 can be transformed into Lagrangian coordinates through a change of variables. Rather than change variables directly in Eqn. 13, a simplification results if one instead first re-writes it, by adding a term to both sides, as done in Farina et al. [10].

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} \left(\phi_s \frac{K(\phi_s)}{\mu} \frac{\partial \sigma_{eff}(\phi_s)}{\partial \phi_s} \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \right) + (v_s - v_c) \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial t} + v_s \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \quad (14)$$

The right hand side here is the material derivative $D_s \phi_s / Dt$. The left hand side is expanded using the product rule of differentiation and introducing the void ratio:

$$e(\mathbf{x}, t) \equiv \frac{1 - \phi_s}{\phi_s}, \quad (15)$$

so that, from Eqn. 3:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial X}{\partial x} \frac{\partial}{\partial X} = \frac{1 + e^0}{1 + e} \frac{\partial}{\partial X}, \quad (16)$$

one arrives at:

$$-(1+e^0)^2 \frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(\frac{1}{1+e} \frac{K(e)}{\mu} \frac{\partial \sigma_{eff}(e)}{\partial e} \frac{\partial e}{\partial X} \right) = \frac{\partial e}{\partial t} \quad (17)$$

This is a transient diffusion equation and can be written as:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial X} \left(D(e) \frac{\partial e}{\partial X} \right) = \frac{\partial e}{\partial t} \quad (18)$$

with the non-linear diffusion coefficient given by Eqn. 19:

$$D(e) = -\frac{1}{\mu} (1+e^0)^2 \left[\frac{1}{1+e} K(e) \frac{\partial \sigma_{eff}(e)}{\partial e} \right] \quad (19)$$

3.5 Boundary and initial conditions

In the Eulerian configuration, there are two moving boundaries, the top and the flow-front. In the Lagrangian configuration, the top boundary is effectively fixed (always at $X = 0$) and there is only the one boundary, the moving flow-front. Due to this convenient simplification, the Lagrangian description will be followed here.

The governing Eqn. 17 is second-order in space and first order in time. Such an equation requires one boundary condition on each boundary: this can be on the primary variable (the void ratio) or its gradient. One also requires an initial condition on the primary variable for the complete domain.

In the RTI case, at the top boundary, $X = 0$, or $x(t) = \delta$, where δ is the distance travelled by the compaction plate, the solid and fluid travel together at the same velocity. Since the relative velocity $v_f - v_s$ is zero, and since the effective stress gradient $\partial \sigma_{eff} / \partial \phi_s$ is (assumed to be) non-zero, one has from Darcy's law, Eqn. 5, the condition on the gradient:

$$\text{Eulerian: } \left. \frac{\partial \phi_s}{\partial x} \right|_{x(t)=\delta(t)} = 0, \quad \text{Lagrangian: } \left. \frac{\partial e}{\partial X} \right|_{X=0} = 0 \quad (20)$$

For the other boundary, representing the interface between the wet and dry regions, consider first the state of the dry material below the flow front: suppose a pressure P_{top} is applied at the initial instant, $t = 0^+$. This pressure transmits through the complete stack and, from equilibrium, $P_{top} = \sigma_{eff} + p$. In the dry portion the fluid pressure, $p = 0$, so $\sigma_{eff}(\phi_s) = P_{top}$ and, using an inverse function: $\phi_s = \sigma_{eff}^{-1}(P_{top})$, uniform throughout the dry portion. The boundary condition applied here is therefore that the void ratio at the flow-front is that corresponding to the solid fraction $\sigma_{eff}^{-1}(P_{top})$.

The initial condition is that, in the wet portion, at $t = 0^+$, i.e. the carrier material, $p = P_{top}$ and $\sigma_{eff} = 0$, so $\phi_s = \sigma_{eff}^{-1}(0)$, i.e. the void ratio is that corresponding to zero effective stress.

3.6 Resin flow

Referring once again to Fig. 3, one can see that as compression commences at $t = 0$, resin flow into the reinforcement ensues. The location of the fluid-solid interface (flow front) is denoted by $s(t)$. In general, there are three different effective stress functions required to fully define the functions which appear in Eqn. 17: the (wet) carrier, σ_{eff}^1 , the wet reinforcement, σ_{eff}^{2w} , and the dry reinforcement, σ_{eff}^{2d} , as indicated in the figure; the superscript “w” denotes the compaction stress of a wet reinforcement and “d” denotes the response of a dry reinforcement, Fig. 3. There are in addition, two permeability functions of the volume fraction, one for the carrier, K^1 , and one for the reinforcement, K^2 , Fig. 3.

4 MODELLING

4.1 Finite element solution in COMSOL

The finite element based multi-physics code COMSOL contains several options for solving PDEs (and ODEs) of various forms. The RTI governing equation developed here can be solved using the “Coefficient Form PDE” interface available in the Mathematics Module in COMSOL. The study is set to time dependent and the governing equation (Eqn. 17) is rearranged into the appropriate form to allow the relevant coefficients to be defined. Fortunately, many of the coefficients in the general coefficient form PDE are zero and we are left with an equation involving only the diffusion coefficient “ c ” (Eqn. 19) and a damping or mass coefficient “ d_a ” as shown below in Eqn. 21.

$$e \frac{\partial^2 e}{\partial t^2} + d_a \frac{\partial e}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (-c \nabla e - \alpha e + \gamma) + \beta \cdot \nabla e + \alpha e = f \quad (21)$$

$$\nabla = \left(\frac{\partial}{\partial x_1}, \dots, \frac{\partial}{\partial x_n} \right)$$

To match Eqn. 17, the equation is rearranged so that “ d_a ” becomes 1 and “ c ” becomes the non-linear diffusion coefficient as given in Eqn. 19 (as $D(e)$). The only unknown in the equation is then “ e ”, the void ratio and $K(e)$ and $(\partial \sigma_{eff}(e))/\partial e$ which are derived functions from the experimental permeability and compaction data. These functions are created as “interpolation” or “analytical” functions” in COMSOL and are called up by the PDE solver. $K(e)$ represents the variation in the permeability for any given void ratio e , while $(\partial \sigma_{eff}(e))/\partial e$ the derivative of the compaction stress for any given e . Two sets of these functions are created for each material (as specified in Section 3.6) over a given range and are then assigned to different domains representing the carrier and NCF material within the entire stack. In COMSOL, two coefficient form PDEs need to be coupled and solved together as we have two different materials with very different material properties (i.e. compaction and permeability) in our problem. Functions for $\sigma_{eff}(e)$ and its inverse $\sigma_{eff}^{-1}(e)$ are also created and are used to define the boundary conditions and the calculation of other output parameters such as the fluid pressure and reinforcement (effective) stress over the total stack height for any given applied pressure input. Geometrically, the 1D model appears as shown in Fig. 6. The compaction direction in this case is in the x direction (note that these lower case x ’s refer here to the Lagrangian/material coordinates). Initially, the simulation begins with two domains, “Domain 1” representing the saturated carrier domain and “Domain 2” an infinitesimally small initial filling of the NCF domain. For both domains, an element size of 0.05 mm has been assigned. The boundary and initial conditions for the simulation can be seen in Fig. 6. In order to calculate the movement of the flow front in an explicit FEA scheme the “Deformed Geometry” physics module is also used and coupled to the PDE physics. In this module, one can define the necessary geometrical changes required to visualise the flow front progression. Two geometric entities defining the length of both domains are linked to the creation of the mesh used to solve the problem. For each time step, the Lagrangian mesh is updated and new elements are created when necessary representing the

progression of the flow front based on calculations of the fluid and solid velocity which occur in the previous time step.

Figure 6: Geometric representation and boundary and initial condition definitions as defined for the 1D RTI model setup in COMSOL.

4.2 Finite element solution in MATLAB

A finite element approach is also used to solve the problem in MATLAB. The non-linear governing Eqn. 18 was discretised using linear elements for the void ratio, leading to:

$$e_1 \int_0^{x_f} D(e) \frac{dN_1}{dX} \frac{dN_j}{dX} dX + e_2 \int_0^{x_f} D(e) \frac{dN_2}{dX} \frac{dN_j}{dX} dX \quad (22)$$

$$= \left[\omega(X) D(e) \frac{\partial e}{\partial X} \right]_0^{x_f} - \dot{e}_1 \int_0^{x_f} N_1 N_j dX - \dot{e}_2 \int_0^{x_f} N_2 N_j dX$$

where the N_i are the linear shape functions. Interpolating the diffusivity linearly over each element, approximating the diffusivity nodal values by their values at a previous time step, $D_i(t) \approx D_i(t - \Delta t)$ converting to local coordinates $\xi = [-1, +1]$, and carrying out the integrations leads to the element equations:

$$\frac{L_e^2}{6} \begin{bmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 1 & 2 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \dot{e}_1 \\ \dot{e}_2 \end{bmatrix} + D_i \begin{bmatrix} +1 & -1 \\ -1 & +1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_1 \\ e_2 \end{bmatrix} = L_e \begin{bmatrix} -(De')_{\xi=-1} \\ +(De')_{\xi=+1} \end{bmatrix} \quad (23)$$

where L_e is the element length, and D_i is the average Diffusion coefficient over the element: $D_i = \frac{1}{2}(D_i + D_{i+1})$. The Finite Element (FE) equations were assembled using a backward difference time integration:

$$[\mathbf{C} + \Delta t \mathbf{K}] \Delta \mathbf{e} = \Delta t [\mathbf{F}(t + \Delta t) - \mathbf{K} \mathbf{e}(t)], \quad \mathbf{e}(t + \Delta t) = \mathbf{e}(t) + \Delta \mathbf{e} \quad (24)$$

where \mathbf{C} , \mathbf{K} , \mathbf{F} are, respectively, the capacitance matrix, stiffness matrix and force vector.

In order to move the flow-front forward, an implicit scheme was developed such that the fluid reached precisely the next node in the fixed mesh in a given time step. For this purpose, it follows directly from Darcy's law that the velocity of fluid relative to solid at the flow front node is:

$$v_f^{n+1} - v_s^{n+1} = -\frac{1}{e^{n+1}} \left[D(e) \lambda \frac{de}{dX} \right]^{(n)} = \frac{e^{(n)} - e^*}{e^*} \left[\frac{D(e^{(n)}) \lambda^{(n)}}{L_e^{(n)}} \right] \quad (25)$$

where $e^* = e^{n+1}$ is the known void ratio at the flow front node, λ is the stretch (ratio of new length to original length of an element), and the term inside the brackets is evaluated over the last element. The time taken for the fluid to travel one element is then:

$$\Delta t = \frac{a}{e^{(n)} - e^*}, \quad a = \left(L_e^{(n)} L_f^{(0)} \right) \frac{1}{D(e^{(n)})} e^* \quad (26)$$

Substituting 25 into 24 leads to a system of non-linear equations which were solved using a standard Newton-Raphson algorithm:

$$\left[\mathbf{K}_T(\mathbf{e}^{i-1}) \right] \Delta \mathbf{e}^i = -\mathbf{R}(\mathbf{e}^{i-1}), \quad \mathbf{K}_T(\mathbf{e}^{i-1}) = \left. \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \mathbf{e}} \right|_{\mathbf{e}^{(i-1)}}, \quad \mathbf{e}^i = \mathbf{e}^{i-1} + \Delta \mathbf{e}^i \quad (27)$$

The residual vector \mathbf{R} and tangent matrix \mathbf{K}_T are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{R} &= \mathbf{C} [\mathbf{e}(t + \Delta t) - \mathbf{e}(t)] - \frac{a}{e^{(n)}(t + \Delta t) - e^*} [\mathbf{F}(t + \Delta t) - \mathbf{K}(\mathbf{e}(t + \Delta t))] \\ \frac{\partial \mathbf{R}}{\partial \mathbf{e}} &= \frac{1}{a} \mathbf{C} [\mathbf{e}(t + \Delta t) - \mathbf{e}(t)] \otimes \frac{\partial e^{(n)}(t + \Delta t)}{\partial \mathbf{e}(t + \Delta t)} + \frac{e^{(n)}(t + \Delta t) - e^*}{a} \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{K} \end{aligned} \quad (28)$$

Once the fluid reaches the end of the reinforcement, the equations can be solved implicitly with any specified time step. In this case, Eqns. 24 are linear and can be solved directly.

4.3 Results

Once solved in either of the two schemes, a variety of outputs are available including 1D graphical plots of the reduction in thickness of the RTI stack as a result of the applied pressure over time (Fig. 7 (left)), or the change in thickness through the entire stack (Fig. 7 (right)). In the test case shown in Figs. 7 and 8, realistic material compaction data, a resin viscosity of 0.3 Pa.s and an applied pressure of 1 bar have been used. An initial expansion takes place over the first 2 seconds of compaction while the NCF material begins to fill. The entire stack then slowly compacts to steady state, which in this case is reached in about 25 seconds. Note that in Fig. 7 (right) the stack is fixed at the top of the graph, so the positions are given relative to this reference point. A negative value of x indicates the slight expansion of the stack.

More complex 3D surface plots showing the hydrodynamic compaction and filling behavior of the carrier and NCF are given in Fig. 8 (left and right) which show the development of the fiber volume fraction for each of the two materials versus time for any given Lagrangian/material coordinate position. The plots are again shown for the same test case presented in Fig. 7. It can be seen that in the current solution both materials tend towards the same void ratio (or fiber volume fraction). The steady state solution to Eqn. 17 is therefore a constant void ratio given by the value at the boundary. In

reality, the fluid pressure tends to zero and the effective stress throughout the stack tends to the applied load, and hence to a state where there are constant but two different void ratios in the carrier and reinforcement. This becomes of particular importance and needs to be considered when the two materials used in the RTI process exhibit highly different compaction behavior.

Figure 7: Plots of the change in overall stack thickness (left) and change in spatial coordinates, i.e. the actual positions of the nodes in space for the entire RTI stack (right) over time.

Figure 8: Surface plots of resulting fiber volume fraction as a function of the Lagrangian/material coordinate and time in seconds for a selected material configuration, resin viscosity and pressure application of 1 bar for the carrier material (left) and NCF material (right).

5 CONCLUSIONS

In the current paper, the framework for a 1D model for the numerical simulation of the RTI processes has been formulated and developed. To solve the governing equation along with its applied boundary and initial conditions, the problem has been setup in COMSOL and also coded in MATLAB. In both cases, a variety of outputs are available including the evolution of hydrodynamic compaction, filling time of the reinforcement and information on the final thicknesses of the two materials. Further work will focus on developing the model to better handle materials with highly different compaction behavior along with the validation of this model using experimental trials and numerical parameter studies to help select the optimum materials and processing parameters for the process.

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REFERENCES

- [1] K. Ann-Sofi Jönsson and B. T. L. Jönsson, Fluid Flow in Compressible Porous Media: I: Steady-State Conditions, *AICHE Journal*, Vol. 38, No. 9, 1992, pp. 1340-1348.
- [2] K. Ann-Sofi Jönsson and B. T. L. Jönsson, Fluid Flow in Compressible Porous Media: II: Dynamic Behavior, *AICHE Journal*, Vol. 38, No. 9, 1992, pp. 1349-1356.
- [3] T. Ouahbi, A. Saouab, J. Bréard, P. Ouagne, S. Chatel, Modelling of hydro-mechanical coupling in infusion processes, *Composites Part A*, Vol. 38, Issue 7, 2007, pp. 1646-1654.
- [4] P. Simacek, S. G. Advani and S.A. Lobst, Modeling Flow in Compression Resin Transfer Molding for Manufacturing of Complex Lightweight High-Performance Automotive Parts, *J. Compos. Mater.*, 42, p 2523, 2008.
- [5] P. Bhat, J. Merotte, P. Simacek, S. G. Advani, Process analysis of compression resin transfer molding, *Composites Part A*, Vol. 40, 2009, pp. 431-441.
- [6] J. Merotte, P. Simacek, S. G. Advani, Resin flow analysis with fiber preform deformation in through thickness direction during Compression Resin Transfer Molding, *Composites Part A*, Vol. 41, 2010, pp. 881-887.
- [7] M. Danzi, F. Klunker and P. Ermanni, Experimental validation of through-thickness resin flow model in the consolidation of saturated porous media. *J. Compos. Mater.*, Vol. 51(17), 2017, pp. 2467-2475.
- [8] F. Klunker, M. Danzi and P. Ermanni, Fiber deformation as a result of fluid injection: modeling and validation in the case of saturated permeability measurements in through thickness direction. *J. Compos. Mater.*, Vol. 49(9), 2014, pp. 1091-1105.
- [9] L. Preziosi, D. D. Joseph and G.S. Beavers, Infiltration of initially dry deformable porous media, *Int. J. Multiphase Flow.*, Vol. 22, No. 6, 1996, pp. 1205-1222.
- [10] A. Farina, P. Cocito and G. Boretto, Flow in deformable porous media: Modelling and simulations of compression moulding processes. *Mathl. Comput. Modelling*, Vol. 26, No. 11, 1997, pp. 1-15.
- [11] L. Billi and A. Farina, Unidirectional infiltration in deformable porous media: Mathematical modelling and self-similar solution. *Quarterly of applied mathematics*, Vol. 58, No. 1, 2000, pp. 85-101.
- [12] B. Willenbacher, D. May and P. Mitschang, Determining the capillary pressure of engineering textiles, *Proceedings of the FPCM-14 – The 14th International Conference on Flow Processing in Composite Materials*, Luleå, Sweden, May 30th-June 1st, 2018.
- [13] J. I. Siddique, A. Ahmed, A. Aziz and C. M. Khalique, A review of mixture theory for deformable porous media and applications. *Appl. Sci.* Vol. 7, No. 917, 2017, pp. 1-15.